

INDENTATION FAILURE OF FOAM CORED SANDWICH STRUCTURES SUBJECTED TO ELEVATED TEMPERATURES

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ABSTRACT

This research explores the influence of elevated temperatures on local indentation failure of polymer foam cored sandwich structures with laminated glass fibre reinforced polymer face sheets. In particular, a simple analytical model to predict the interfacial normal stresses at the top face sheet and its local deflection at elevated temperatures is presented and validated against experimental observations. A sandwich beam loaded in three-point bending with an induced through-thickness elevated temperature profile, was studied experimentally and by means of analytical and finite element models (FEM). In the experiment, the through-thickness temperature gradient was induced with an infrared lamp pointing at the top face sheet, while the local displacement and strain fields near the applied point load were recorded by Digital Image Correlation (DIC). The simple analytical model proposed, which accounts for temperature degraded/reduced foam core properties, superimposes the local response, approximated by the classical Winkler foundation model, and the global response, obtained by sandwich beam theory. It is shown, that the simple analytical model and the finite element (FE) models are capable of accurately predicting the local load response and core stresses of foam cored composite sandwich structures subjected to simultaneous localised mechanical loading and elevated temperatures. The simple analytical model has therefore the potential to become a preliminary design tool to determine the critical core crushing load at elevated temperatures.

1 INTRODUCTION

Lightweight composite sandwich structures with glass fibre reinforced polymer (GFRP) face sheets and polymer foam core materials (such as polyvinyl chloride - PVC) are widely used for structural applications across, for example, the marine, transportation, wind energy and offshore industries. They are valued for their excellent stiffness and strength to weight ratios combined with their affordability for low to medium cost applications [1]. However, they are prone to indentation failure when localised loading is applied and they are sensitive to elevated temperatures, as the foam cores used typically display significant softening and reduction of stiffness and strength already in the temperature range of 50-70 °C. This is well within the operational service environment of typical applications such as ship and train structures or wind turbine blades exposed to e.g. sun light or heat radiation of machinery.

Growing concern in industry and academia has led to research into the thermal behaviour of polymer foam sandwich core materials as well as foam cored sandwich structures. Zhang et al. [2] obtained the temperature dependency of the through-thickness tensile and compressive Young's modulus of DIAB Divinycell cross-linked PVC H100, H130 and H200 [3] foam cores in the temperature range of 25-90 °C experimentally. Taher et al. [4 - 5] extended the characterization of Divinycell H100 at elevated temperatures with experimental measurements of both tensile and compressive strength and strain to failure in through-thickness and in-plane directions.

Based on accurate measurements of the temperature dependent foam core properties, Zhang et al. [6 - 7] investigated the effect of temperature degraded foam properties on structural components and investigated the failure mode of face sheet wrinkling and the bending behaviour of foam cored sandwich structures leading to core shear failure under combined mechanical and thermal loading. In parallel, Palleti et. al [8] investigated the thermomechanical interaction effects on the failure modes of a foam

cored sandwich beam subjected to elevated temperatures with a special emphasis on the development of a nonlinear FE material model based on the generalized Hill anisotropic plasticity model to capture the highly nonlinear response of foam core materials at elevated temperatures. In these studies, the top face sheet of a sandwich beam specimen was exposed to an infrared lamp, inducing a temperature gradient through the core thickness. This is a realistic scenario that can be found wherever a heat source, such as sun radiation or machinery, is positioned on one side of a sandwich panel. Digital Image Correlation (DIC) was subsequently employed to capture the displacement and strain fields at the side surface of the beam.

Indentation failure of sandwich structures at room temperature has been studied extensively and several analytical modelling approaches have been proposed. The simplest analytical indentation models for sandwich structures are based on the superposition of the global bending response, obtained by sandwich beam or panel theory, with the local response obtained by using the Winkler foundation model [9]. The adoption of the foundation model on sandwich structures was introduced by Thomsen in [1]. Later, Olsson [10] presented an indentation model very similar to the former but additionally proposed two different foundation moduli for thick cores to calculate local deflections and stresses respectively. Both authors highlighted the dependency of the foundation modulus K_z on the thickness of the core and proposed different formulations in each case.

The literature review has shown, that foam cored composite sandwich structures are increasingly being used for applications that involve elevated temperatures (up to about 90 °C). However, all the research identified in open literature on indentation failure has been conducted at room temperature, whereas indentation failure at elevated temperature has never been addressed before. The present study fills the knowledge gap and addresses the problem of localized loading of polymer foam cored sandwich structures subjected to elevated temperatures. The aim is to improve the understanding of the indentation mechanism at elevated temperatures, and to develop guidelines and methodologies for the design of foam cored sandwich structures to avoid premature failure through core crushing at elevated temperature.

2 METHODOLOGY

Figure 1 visualizes the studied sandwich beam with a temperature gradient imposed through the foam core thickness, leading to degraded mechanical properties of the foam core. The influence of the temperature on the GFRP face sheet material was judged to be negligible and was ignored. The simple three-point bending configuration allows the simultaneous study of the global bending of the sandwich beam and the local bending of the top face sheet near the point load. Indentation failure is defined as the state where the transverse (through thickness) compressive stress or strain in the core reaches the compressive transverse strength or strain to failure of the core at the top face sheet to core interface.

Figure 1: Sandwich beam loaded in three-point bending with an applied temperature gradient

An iterative design process, using the simple analytical model, aiming to identify a sandwich specimen configuration where initial failure is by core crushing (indentation failure) was conducted. This led to a sandwich specimen with span 0.4 m, width 57 mm, core thickness 45 mm and face sheet thickness 2.27 mm. Divinycell H100 [3] from DIAB was selected as core material due to its known temperature dependency derived in previous studies. The face sheets were laminated from ten layers of

unidirectional E-Glass/Epoxy prepreg RP-528 from PRF composites and cured at 120 °C [11]. The face sheet laminates (layup [0₁₀]) were bonded to the foam core using SA80 adhesive epoxy film from Gurit [12].

The experiment was conducted on an Instron servo-hydraulic test machine with an infrared lamp suspended from the crosshead, pointing at the top face sheet surface of the specimen to induce a through-thickness temperature gradient. Displacement and strain maps are obtained by Digital Image Correlation (DIC) in the area of interest near the indenter. The specimen was painted mat black, and a white speckle pattern was applied in the area of interest with a spray can. The temperature gradient was monitored with six thermocouples attached to the foam core and with an infrared camera pointing at the front surface of the specimen. The experimental arrangement is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Experimental set-up (left), and the field of view in way of the indenter with a detailed view of the speckle pattern (right).

The analytical model assumes, that the total response at the outer face sheet of the sandwich beam can be found by superimposing the independently calculated local and global responses. The global response was computed using classical sandwich beam theory [1] that was modified to account for temperature degraded/reduced core properties (E_c and G_c) in the computation of the bending stiffness D and the shear stiffness S [7]. The local response was approximated by adopting the Winkler foundation model. Thus, the top face sheet is considered to be supported by an elastic foundation (the core), modelled as continuously distributed tension/compression springs as shown in Figure 3 and suggested by Thomsen in [1] for a sandwich beam with uniform through thickness mechanical properties of the sandwich core.

Figure 3: Schematic of the Winkler foundation model with the foundation modulus K_z and the interfacial normal force per unit width q_z .

In this paper, the model is modified to account for the temperature dependent transverse compressive stiffness of the core and the core foundation stiffness K_z is computed as follows:

$$K_z = 0.28 E_{c\text{ AVG}} \left(\frac{E_{c\text{ AVG}}}{D_f} \right)^{\frac{1}{3}}$$

Where $E_{c\text{ AVG}}$ is the core compressive Young's modulus averaged over the core thickness, and D_f is the bending stiffness of the top face (which is assumed to be independent of temperature). The reader is referred to [13] for a more detailed description.

The FE analyses were conducted using the commercial software ANSYS APDL 17.0. A 2D plane stress model was constructed using PLANE82 8-node quadratic structural elements. To account for the temperature dependent core material properties, the core was divided into horizontal slices with a constant temperature. The temperature in the centre of each slice was computed based on the input of the top face sheet temperature T_t and the bottom face sheet temperature T_b assuming a linear through-thickness temperature gradient. The mechanical properties were reduced per the regression formula derived in [2].

Initially, a linear elastic material model was used. It became apparent that the core material exhibits strongly nonlinear behaviour even before reaching core crushing stress levels. Naturally, for polymer materials, nonlinear effects became even more pronounced at higher temperatures. This led to the development of a second nonlinear FE model that included the nonlinear contact problem between indenter and sandwich beam, geometric nonlinearity, as was anticipated in the indentation region at higher loads, and most importantly a nonlinear material model for the foam core. Hill's generalized anisotropic plasticity model was adopted as proposed in [8].

3 Extract of Results

In this chapter, selected experimental results for the $T_t = 50^\circ\text{C}$ load case are presented. Reference is made to [13] for the full set of results, covering the temperature range from 25 - 90 °C.

Figure 4 compares the DIC and nonlinear FE displacement maps at $T_t = 50^\circ\text{C}$ and $P = 1000\text{ N}$. It is observed that the experimentally and numerically obtained overall deflection patterns as well as the maximum deflections at the top face sheet to core interface are in close agreement.

Figure 4: Experimental (left) and nonlinear FE results (right) - transverse local deflection fields at $P = 1000\text{ N}$ for $T_t = 50^\circ\text{C}$.

Figure 5 compares experimental and FE displacement and strain profiles at midspan for three different load steps at $T_t = 50^\circ\text{C}$. It is observed that the experimental and FE displacement profiles correspond well. The nonlinear FE model predicts higher maximum deflections near the top face sheet than the linear model and therefore agrees better with the experimental data. The analytical model only provides the displacement at the top face sheet, but the predictions are in good agreement with both the experimental data and the nonlinear FE model.

The nonlinear FE model predicts the strain profiles and the maximum strain at the top face sheet to core interface more accurately than the linear FE model, but still under-predicts the compressive core strains by about 25 % in comparison to the experimental data. However, the nonlinear model predicts

the parabolic strain decay through the core thickness. Moreover, it could be tuned to give a better match, because the choice of the transverse compressive yield point in the nonlinear material model has a significant effect on the accuracy of the nonlinear FE model.

Figure 5: Through-thickness local deflection (left) and strain (right) profiles at P = 500 (black), 1000 (blue) and 1500 N (green) for $T_i = 50\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$

Figure 6 shows the interfacial normal stresses along the top face sheet to core interface as predicted by the FE and analytical models for two different load and temperature cases. The general behaviour of the analytical model, which is best characterized by the predicted wave length of the local face sheet bending effects (due to indentation) and the maximum value at midspan, is similar to the response predicted by the FE models. Generally, the analytical model tends to underestimate the maximum stress when compared to the FE solutions, but surprisingly the agreement improves at elevated temperatures.

Figure 6: Interfacial normal stress distributions: analytical model vs. FE predictions.

In summary, it has been demonstrated that the developed FE models, which account for temperature degraded/reduced foam core properties, are capable of predicting local deflections and strains that agree well with the experimental data. Furthermore, the analytical model based on sandwich beam theory and the Winkler foundation model, both extended to account for temperature degraded/reduced foam core properties, predicts top face sheet deflection and interfacial normal stresses that correspond well with the FE model predictions. Hence, it is possible to compute the critical core stresses leading to core crushing and indentation failure at elevated temperatures for the investigated beam by use of both the FE and analytical models. The analytical model is considerably simpler and faster to use and is therefore well suited for preliminary design purposes.

4 CONCLUSIONS

A foam cored sandwich beam with laminated GFRP face sheets subjected to a point load and a through-thickness temperature gradient was studied experimentally, analytically, and by means of a linear and nonlinear FE model. The aim was to evaluate how the temperature degraded foam core properties will affect the critical core crushing stresses and hence the structural integrity of a foam cored sandwich beam.

Based on the experimental evidence and underpinned by linear and nonlinear FE results, a simple approximate analytical model is proposed that can predict the local face sheet load response and the core stresses at elevated temperatures. For the investigated foam cored sandwich beam configuration, both FE model predictions and experimental data suggested a complete decay of the localized effects through the core thickness for all temperature cases. This means, that the global and local bending response can be superimposed, and that no interactions between the face sheets are to be expected due to local indentation. This corresponds to the fundamental restrictive assumption adopted for the approximate analytical models that was investigated in this research. Accordingly, the adoption of the simple analytical model frame work, which is based on the assumption that the loaded face sheet can be considered as supported by an elastic foundation, has been validated.

It has been shown, that the proposed analytical model is able to predict core stresses at elevated temperatures with reasonable accuracy, and with a similar degree of accuracy as observed at room temperature. This shows that averaging the degraded/reduced transverse compressive Young's moduli over the core thickness to calculate the foundation modulus K_z is a simple and efficient way to predict indentation failure at elevated temperatures.

The major discrepancy between the predictions of the analytical model and the experimental data and the FE model predictions does not arise from the implemented temperature dependency of the core stiffness properties, but can be attributed to the dependency of the foundation modulus K_z on the core thickness. To resolve this, more sophisticated elastic foundation models would have to be considered, where especially the through-thickness decay of local effects would have to be improved. However, this was considered to be beyond the scope of the present study which focused on the effects of elevated temperatures, and thus was not attempted.

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